

Mixed Tsallis - Kaniadakis Scenario?

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We note that in both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases, one infers a function F such that $F(p)=x=-e_i/T$. In the Tsallis case, $F = \ln_q(p) = (p^{1-q} - 1) / (1-q)$ and in the Kaniadakis, $F = \ln_k(p) = 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k})$. In the $1-q = k \rightarrow 0$ limit, both \ln_q and $\ln_k \rightarrow \ln$.

We also note that in general, the unnormalized p 's for the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases differ, e.g. Tsallis has $\exp_q = \{1 + (1-q)x\}^{1/(1-q)}$ and Kaniadakis, $\{\sqrt{1+kkxx} + kx\}^{1/k}$. We argue, however, that these are both linked with a quadratic equation and propose a mixed Tsallis-Kaniadakis: $F(p) = a (p^k - 1) / k + (1-a)/2k \{p^k - p^{-k}\}$, where $0 \leq a \leq 1$. In the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit, one obtains $F(p) = \ln(p)$ and we solve for p as a quadratic solution and show that it becomes $\exp(x)$ (for $k \rightarrow 0$) where $x = -e_i/T$, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution. In other words, one may obtain skewed Kaniadakis \ln_k forms $a_1 p^k - b_1 p^{-k} + \text{constant}$ by combining weighted Tsallis and Kaniadakis forms.

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Cases

The Tsallis case is based on:

$$\ln_q(p(e_i)) = x = -e_i/T \quad \text{where} \quad \ln_q(p) = \{p^{1-q} - 1\} / \{1-q\} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{and } p(e_i) = \{1 + (1-q)x\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Tsallis entropy is: } -\{\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i)^q - 1\} / \{1-q\} \quad ((3))$$

In the Kaniadakis case, one has:

$$\ln_k(p(e_i)) = x = -e_i/T \quad \text{where} \quad \ln_k(p) = \{p^k - p^{-k}\} / (2k) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{And } p(e_i) = \{\sqrt{1+kkxx} + kx\}^{1/k} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{with Kaniadakis entropy} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

We note that ((2)) and ((5)) appear as quadratic equation solutions and set $1-q = k$.

In the limit $k \rightarrow 0$ $\ln_q \rightarrow \ln$ and $\ln_k \rightarrow \ln$ and ((2)) $\rightarrow \exp(-e_i/T)$ as does ((4))

Hybrid Tsallis-Kaniadakis Case

We consider a hybrid Tsallis-Kaniadakis case using a weighted sum of \ln_q and \ln_k , i.e.

$$a \ln_q(p) + (1-a) \ln_k(p) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where } 0 \leq a \leq 1$$

((6)) is guaranteed to yield $\ln(p)$ for $k \rightarrow 0$, $q \rightarrow 1$. We next seek a solution for p in this hybrid.

We write:

$$F(p) = x = -e_i/T = a/k (p^k - 1) + (1-a)/(2k) (p^k - p^{-k}) \quad ((7))$$

This leads to a skewed type of Kaniadakis \ln_k form. We assume that:

$p(e_i/T) = M^{1/k}$ where M is a function of x . One may then solve ((7)) for M .

$2kx = 2aM - 2a + (1-a)M - (1-a)/M$ ((8)) which is a quadratic in M with solution:

$$M = \{ a+kx \pm \sqrt{(a+kx)(a+kx) + (1-a)(1+a)} \} / (a+1) \quad ((8))$$

M should be >0 and so the plus sign should be chosen, i.e.

$$M = \{ a+kx + \sqrt{(a+kx)(a+kx) + (1-a)(1+a)} \} / (a+1) \quad ((9))$$

In the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit $\sqrt{(a+kx)(a+kx) + (1-a)(1+a)} \approx 1 + kax$.

Thus, in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit, $M = \{(a+1) + kx(a+1)\} / (1+a) = 1 + kx$

So $M^{1/k} \rightarrow \exp(x) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ which is the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.

As a result,

$$p(x) = \{ a+kx + \sqrt{(a+kx)(a+kx) + (1-a)(1+a)} \} / (a+1)^{1/k} \text{ where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((10))$$

For a mixed Tsallis-Kaniadakis system with a being the Tsallis weight and $1-a$, the Kaniadakis. The solution ((10)) appears to be more general than the usual Kaniadakis result.

Possible Issues

Even though one may create a weighted Tsallis-Kaniadakis $\ln_q + \ln_k$, one should note that Tsallis entropy is $\sum_i p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i))$ while Kaniadakis is: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i))$. This, in turn, is linked with maximization schemes associated with an a priori constraint: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i$ for Tsallis and $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i$ for the Kaniadakis case. The hybrid approach simply considers an $F(p) = x = -e_i/T$ such that for $1-q=k=0$, one obtains $F(p) = \ln(p)$ and $p \rightarrow \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider a weighted Tsallis-Kaniadakis hybrid: $F(p) = x = -e_i/T = a \ln_q(p) + (1-a) \ln_k(p)$ where $1-q=k$. For $k=0$, $q=1$ this automatically yields $\ln(p)$. We find the solution:

$p(x) = \{ a+kx + \sqrt{ (a+kx)(a+kx) + (1-a)(1+a) } \} / (a+1)$ power $1/k$ where $x=-ei/t$

and in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit it yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann result, $\exp(-ei/T)$.